

Seroprevalence of Blood Borne Pathogens Among Healthy Blood Donors in Lahore, Pakistan

Mehak Zahra^{1*}, Irum Shahbaz¹, Muhammad Salman Munir Malik¹, Muhammad Tahir Ishaq¹, Hafiz Ghulam Murtaza Saleem¹

¹University Institute of Medical Laboratory Technology, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, The University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

*zahra.eeman@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Seropositivity for Hepatitis B virus (HBsAg), hepatitis C virus (HCV), Human Immune Deficiency virus (HIV) and Syphilis are of the highest public health concern. Transfusion of contaminated blood is one of the major causes of spread of blood borne diseases.

Objective:

To find out the seroprevalence of blood borne pathogens among the healthy blood donors in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methods:

The sample size of 1674 healthy blood donors was based upon pre-established criteria of body weight, hemoglobin and interviewing about their previous medical and donation history. Venous blood was collected from blood donors for testing of HBsAg, HIV, HCV and syphilis through Immuno Chroma Tography (ICT) method.

Results:

77 out of total 1674 blood donors were found positive for different blood borne diseases. Eighteen (23.38%) were found positive for HBsAg, 38 (49%) for HCV, 2 (2.6%) for HIV and 19 (25%) for syphilis. Blood group A+ was observed the most prevalent donors and the overall incidence of blood borne pathogens was found significantly high in this blood group. The prevalence of HCV was high (31.6%) between the age group of 26-33 years, whereas the incidence of Syphilis (47.4%) and HBsAg (61.1%) were considerably high between the 18-25 years of ages.

Conclusions:

The stringent selection and complete screening of donor's blood using standard methods (good

quality ICT test kits), which were highly suggested to make sure the safety of blood for the recipient as well as donor.

Keywords:

Seropositivity, Hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), Human immune deficiency virus (HIV), Syphilis

Introduction:

Donating blood is an active way of helping others and the whole of society. It is voluntary procedure. Donating blood can save many lives, it can be used individually in specific conditions for different patients, if blood is separated into its constituents such as red blood cells, platelets and plasma, because millions of people need blood each year¹. Some may need blood during surgery or after an accident. Healthy ones can donate blood to those who lost blood in the violence of the attack^{2,3}. In developed countries, most blood donors owe volunteers who donate blood without any personal benefit. In poor countries, donors usually give or donate blood to their family or friends when they need a transfusion. Many donors donate blood as an act of charity, but in those countries that allow paid donation some donors are paid and in that cases blood transfusion is not safe. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations, regular voluntary blood donors are the safest group of donors that's why the prevalence of blood borne infections rate is lowest among these donors as compare to paid donors⁴. The safety of blood transfusion is major source of concern in developing countries⁵. The prevalence of transmissible blood-borne infections is quite high in the developing countries⁶. In Pakistan both HCV and HBV infections are highly prevalent and there is a significant threat of

human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) spread across the country⁷. In most of the cases hepatic viruses HCV and HBV remain unnoticed because of their asymptomatic nature in the initial phase of infection⁸. Hepatitis B and C can spread through blood and body secretions /fluids and can lead to scarring of liver^{9,10}. Both viruses are contributed in causing major dreadful liver infections, it can also cause liver cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and lymphoma in human around the globe^{11,12}. It was most common in Africa, Central and East Asia¹³. According to an estimation there are 200 million chronic carriers of HCV and 350 to 400 million chronic carriers of HBV¹⁴. Annually 700 000 people die with liver diseases. Almost 90% of persons with hepatitis C infection can be cured by Antiviral medicines therefore the risk of death from liver cancer and cirrhosis will be minimized. Currently no vaccine for hepatitis C virus exists thus the research in this area is ongoing. In 2013 about 11 million new cases occurred¹⁵. Whereas in 2015, due to hepatitis C virus about 167,000 deaths occurred with liver cancer¹⁶. Another major problem in developing countries including Pakistan is sexually transmitted infections (STI's). Due to the lack of proper care and poor nutrition, millions of people suffer from HIV¹⁷. Syphilis is a systemic disease, it can spread very quickly by sexual interaction and blood transfusion^{18, 19}. Blood transfusion is one of its significant routes of its transmission²⁰.

A study was conducted in Ethiopia and found 29.5% the seroprevalence of blood borne pathogens and HCV, HBV, HIV, and syphilis was found with the prevalence of 8.5%, 9.5%, 6.4%, and 7.5%, respectively²¹. Hussain A *et al.*, 2015 indicated 5.92% prevalence of infection in blood donations and observed HCV infection with highest the prevalence of 3.44% followed by HBV (2.32%), *Treponema pallidum* (TP) (0.07%), and Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (0.01%)²². Pakistan faces a ceaselessly expanding demand of blood transfusions particularly on

account of thalassemia, hemodialysis and hemophilia patients alongside street side wounds. In Pakistan, there are around 100,000 patients of thalassemia major with their lives absolutely subject to blood transfusions²³.

The study was aimed to evaluate the incidence of Hepatitis B virus (HBsAg), hepatitis C virus (HCV), Human immune deficiency virus (HIV) and Syphilis among the blood donors and to check the frequency of different blood groups.

Methods:

This was a retrospective study based on the data of healthy blood donors, suspected with different infectious diseases, visiting hospital for blood donation from June 2016 to December 2016. Study was conducted in General Hospital Lahore, Pakistan. The sample size of study was 1674 healthy blood donors. The selection of blood donors was based upon pre-established criteria of body weight, hemoglobin and interviewing about their previous medical and donation history. The donors were informed about the objectives of current study before bleed. Venous blood was collected by using sterile syringe from each blood donor, and sample was placed in sterile test tubes for testing of HBsAg, HIV, HCV and syphilis. The donors with body weight less than 50 Kg were excluded from the sample. ICT method was used to test the HCV, HBV, HIV and syphilis. Antigen/ antibody were detected through one-step qualitative assay using rapid in vitro ICT test kit (SD Bioline antigen/ antibody test) according to the manufacturer's instructions. About 100 µl of serum were added to the sample pad of each rapid test device On a clean rigid bench surface the test device was left undisturbed for 15-20 minutes. In test device a chromogenic indicator (a colored line) in response to the reaction was produced as positive, while the negative reaction was indicated for device without line in test zone. For device quality purpose a colored line was also produced at control point in each test device. The devices without control line were rejected and samples were repeated.

Data were subjected for statistical analysis through SPSS version 25.0.

Results:

Total 1674 healthy blood donors were screened for the presence of infectious diseases like Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, HIV and syphilis using ICT test kits. Out of 1674, 77 blood donors were found positive for different blood borne diseases. 18 (23.38%) were positive for HBsAg, 38 (49%) were positive for HCV and 2 (2.6%) were positive for HIV and 19 (25%) were positive for syphilis, as shown in Table 1.

Test	Positive reaction
HBsAg	18 (23.4%)
HIV	2(2.6%)
HCV	38(49%)
Syphilis	19(25%)
Total	77(100%)

Table 1: Frequency of transfusion transmitted infections among blood donors

Seroprevalence of HBsAg of A+ blood group were observed in 8(30.8%) donors while 1(3.8%) in HIV, 12(46.2%) in HCV and 5(19.2%) in syphilis, as shown in Table 2. Among A- blood group 1(100%) donors were found positive for HIV. The frequency of HBsAg, HCV and Syphilis in donors of B+ blood group was 5(20.83%), 11(45.83%) and 8(33.33%) respectively. In B- blood group 1 donor showed the presence of HCV and 2 donors were found with positive Syphilis. In O+ blood donors the frequency of infectious diseases such as HCV was 13(65%), HBsAg 5(25%), HIV (0%) and syphilis 2(10%). In O- blood group, 1 donor was found with positive HIV, whereas the frequency of Syphilis was 2(100%) in AB+ blood donors.

Infectious diseases	Blood groups						
	A+ (n=26)	A- (n=1)	B+ (n=24)	B- (n=3)	O+ (n=20)	O- (n=1)	AB+ (n=2)
HCV	12(46.2%)	-	11(45.83%)	1(33.3%)	13(65%)	-	-
HBsAg	8(30.8%)	-	5(20.83%)	-	5(25%)	-	-
HIV	1(3.8%)	1(100%)	-	-	-	1(100%)	-
Syphilis	5(19.2%)	-	8(33.33%)	2(66.7%)	2(10%)	-	2(100%)

Table 2: Frequency of infectious diseases in different blood groups among healthy blood donors

The highest prevalence of HCV was found in blood donors with ages among 18-25 years 12(31.6%), 26-33 years 12(31.6%), 34-41 years 10(26.3%), and 42-49 years 4(10.5%). While the occurrence of HBsAg in blood donors with respect to their age groups 18-25, 26-33, 34-4 and 42-49 were 61.1%, 33.3%, 5.6% and 0 respectively, as shown in Table 3. The highest percentage (61.1%) of HBsAg was found in age between 18-25 years of blood donors as compared to 26-49 years age of blood donors. No case of HBsAg positive was found between 42-49 years of blood donors, whereas the incidence of HIV had same percentage of 50 among the ages of 18-25 and 26-33 years. The occurrence of syphilis was high between ages of 18-25 years of blood donors which was 47.4% while 36.8%, 5.3% and 10.5% was found in between 26-33, 34-41 and 42-49 years of blood donors respectively.

Age groups (years)	HCV	HBsAg	HIV	Syphilis
18-25	12(31.6%)	11(61.1%)	1(50%)	9(47.4%)
26-33	12(31.6%)	6(33.3%)	1(50%)	7(36.8%)
34-41	10(26.3%)	1(5.6%)	-	1(5.3%)
42-49	4(10.5%)	-	-	2(10.5%)
Total	38(100%)	18(100%)	2(100%)	19(100%)

Table 3: Seroprevalence of various infectious diseases among healthy blood donors in different age groups

Discussion:

In current study the percentage (49%) of HCV was found relatively high than the other infectious diseases including HIV, syphilis and HBsAg. Manzoor I *et al.*, reported the prevalence of HCV (7.69%) in Lahore²¹, while Ujjan ID *et al.*,²⁴ recorded a prevalence of HCV (8.68%) in

Hyderabad, as compared to current study 49% study population was positive for HCV²². A study conducted in Peshawar during 2017 by Junaid I *et al.*, found the overall 18% prevalence of HCV,²³ which was greater than 8% previously reported amongst the general community of Islamabad, Pakistan²⁴. In another study conducted in Jos, Plateau state, Nigeria Egah DZ *et al.*,²⁵ by presented that the 6% incidence of HCV while current study observed 49% HCV seropositivity. Whereas Isa AH *et al.*,²⁶ found prevalence of HCV 1.8% in blood donors of Kaduna state in Nigeria, which was found less than as compare to present study. It has been reported that prevalence of HBV, HCV and HIV in India, among blood donors reduced from 1.62%, 1.85% and 1.16% (in 2004) to 0.92%, 0.52% and 0.21% (in 2009) respectively²⁷. While current study reported the prevalence of transmissible diseases including Syphilis, HCV, HIV and HBsAg as 25%, 49%, 2.60% and 23.40% respectively²⁷, these results were relatively higher than the previous studies. Whereas the seroprevalence of HBsAg was 23.40% among the healthy blood donors, which was similar to the findings of Chatteraj A *et al.*, Kaur H *et al.*, and Singh B *et al.*,²⁸⁻³⁰. The prevalence of Syphilis was found to be 25% in current study which was much higher than other studies done by 0.85% and Mumtaz S *et al.*, 1.2%²⁷. however study carried out by, Arshad *et al.*,³¹ reported that the frequency of Syphilis was 0.04% in their population. Seroprevalence of HBsAg and HCV noted higher in O+ blood group according to the recent study done by in 2010.³² These findings were much similar to current study such as incidence of HCV was observed significantly high in O+ blood donors. The frequency of infectious diseases like HBsAg, HIV, HCV and Syphilis was observed higher in A+ blood donor rather than other blood groups of study subjects including A-, B+, B-, AB+, AB, O- and O+ blood groups. While the frequency of HCV higher in O+ blood donors. The frequency of HBsAg was significantly higher in A+ blood donor as

compared to B+ blood group donors. In present study, the ages of blood donors varied from 18 to 49 years with a median age of 28 years. The prevalence of HBsAg was indicated higher 61.1%, in youngers (18-25 years) as compare to which reported HBsAg 15.4% in same age group.³³ The increased prevalence of HBsAg was noticed due to the increasing trend of practices like tattooing and immoral behavior in some individuals. In 2004, National Demographic survey indicated the occurrence of HIV in blood donors was 5.5% in the adult population between 18 to 49 years while in current study the prevalence of HIV was 50% between 18 to 33 years blood donors. On the other hand in 2013 a study was carried out in Nigeria by Afolabi A *et al.*, reported no significant variance in the prevalence of HBV, HCV and HIV antibodies among the different age groups of blood donors³⁴, Such as adult between the ages 21-30 showed seropositivity with the maximum number 15(1.0%) of HIV and Hepatitis B infection 21(1.4%) and the seropositivity of HIV among ages 31-40 1(0.1%) were found positive.

Conclusions:

Result indicated the overall prevalence of different infectious diseases (HCV, HBsAg, HIV and Syphilis) with varying frequency among healthy blood donors with no association of infectious diseases with blood groups. The stringent selection and complete screening of donor's blood using standard methods (good quality ICT test kits), which were highly suggested to make sure the safety of blood for the recipient as well as donor.

References:

- 1- Carson JL, Grossman BJ, Kleinman S, Tinmouth AT, Marques MB, Fung MK, Holcomb JB, Illoh O, Kaplan LJ, Katz LM, Rao SV. Red blood cell transfusion: a clinical practice guideline from the AABB. *Annals of internal medicine*. 2012 Jul 3;157(1):49-58.
- 2- Tapko JB, Mainuka P, Diarra-Nama AJ. Status of blood safety in the WHO African region. Report of the 2004 survey. WHO-Afro

- Brazzaville, Congo. 2006. [Last accessed on 05 May, 2019]. Retrieved from: https://www.afro.who.int/sites/default/files/201706/status_blood_safety_who_african_region.pdf
- 3- Waldby C, Mitchell R. Tissue economies: Blood, organs, and cell lines in late capitalism. Duke University Press; 2006 Mar 20.
 - 4- World Health Organization. Screening donated blood for transfusion-transmissible infections: recommendations. World Health Organization; 2010.
 - 5- Nagalo MB, Sanou M, Bisseye C, Kaboré MI, Nebie YK, Kienou K, Kiba A, Dahourou H, Ouattara S, Zongo JD, Simporé J. Seroprevalence of human immunodeficiency virus, hepatitis B and C viruses and syphilis among blood donors in Koudougou (Burkina Faso) in 2009. *Blood transfusion*. 2011 Oct;9(4):419.
 - 6- Kardam P, Mehendiratta M, Rehani S, Kumra M. Seroprevalence and vaccination status of hepatitis B amongst dental health-care workers in North India. *Indian Journal of Gastroenterology*. 2014 Mar 1;33(2):190-1.
 - 7- Asl H, Kazem S, Avijgan M, Mohamadnejad M. High prevalence of HBV, HCV, and HIV infections in gypsy population residing Shahr-e-Kord. *Archives of Iranian Medicine*. 2004;7(1):20-2.
 - 8- Catalani C, Biggeri A, Gottard A, Benvenuti M, Frati E, Cecchini C. Prevalence of HCV infection among health care workers in a hospital in central Italy. *European journal of epidemiology*. 2004 Jan 1;19(1):73-7.
 - 9- Kumar V, Abbas AK, Fausto N, Aster JC. Robbins and Cotran pathologic basis of disease, professional edition e-book. Elsevier health sciences; 2014 Aug 27.
 - 10- Mujeeb SA, Pearce MS. Temporal trends in hepatitis B and C infection in family blood donors from interior Sindh, Pakistan. *BMC Infectious Diseases*. 2008 Dec;8(1):43
 - 11- Ferri C, Sebastiani M, Giuggioli D, Colaci M, Fallahi P, Piluso A, Antonelli A, Zignego AL. Hepatitis C virus syndrome: A constellation of organ- and non-organ specific autoimmune disorders, B-cell non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, and cancer. *World journal of hepatology*. 2015 Mar 27;7(3):327.
 - 12- Rusyn I, Lemon SM. Mechanisms of HCV-induced liver cancer: what did we learn from in vitro and animal studies?. *Cancer letters*. 2014 Apr 10;345(2):210-5.
 - 13- World Health Organization. Hepatitis C. Fact Sheet 164. 1999; 74: 421-428. [Last accessed on 05 May, 2019]. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hepatitis-c>
 - 14- Elzouki AN, Elgamay SM, Zorgani A, Elahmer O. Hepatitis B and C status among health care workers in the five main hospitals in eastern Libya. *Journal of infection and public health*. 2014 Nov 1;7(6):534-41.
 - 15- Vos T, Barber RM, Bell B, Bertozzi-Villa A, Biryukov S, Bolliger I, Charlson F, Davis A, Degenhardt L, Dicker D, Duan L. Global, regional, and national incidence, prevalence, and years lived with disability for 301 acute and chronic diseases and injuries in 188 countries, 1990–2013: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013. *The Lancet*. 2015 Aug 22;386(9995):743-800.
 - 16- Wang H, Naghavi M, Allen C, Barber RM, Bhutta ZA, Carter A, Casey DC, Charlson FJ, Chen AZ, Coates MM, Coggeshall M. Global, regional, and national life expectancy, all-cause mortality, and cause-specific mortality for 249 causes of death, 1980–2015: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015. *The lancet*. 2016 Oct 8;388(10053):1459-544.
 - 17- World Health Organization. Diet, nutrition, and the prevention of chronic diseases: report of a joint WHO/FAO expert consultation.

- World Health Organization; 2003 Apr 22.
- 18-Murray P, Rosenthal Ks, Kobayashi Gs, Pfaller Ma, Medical Microbiology. Arthropods, 2002.
 - 19-Mohammadali F, Pourfathollah A. Association of ABO and Rh blood groups to blood-borne infections among blood donors in Tehran-Iran. Iranian journal of public health. 2014 Jul;43(7):981.
 - 20-Joseph BS, Yi-Gang W, Yang L. Knowledge of Njala campus athletes about abstinence from diseases associated with unsafe sexual practices such as Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome {HIV/AIDS}, Gonorrhoea {GR} and Syphilis {SP}, aimed as primary prevention strategy in minimizing the process of ageing. Journal of Exercise Science and Physiotherapy. 2016 Jan 25;12(1):42.
 - 21-Manzoor I, Hashmi NO, Daud SE, Ajmal SA, Fatima HI, Rasheed ZA, Syed SA. Seroprevalence of transfusion transmissible infections (TTIS) in blood donors. Biomedica. 2009 Jul;25(10):154-8.
 - 22-Hussain A, Mumtaz HM, Aslam MS, Abbas Z. Seroprevalence of transfusion based transmissible infections among clinically healthy donors in the community of Multan. Pakistan. J Inf Mol Biol. 2015;3(2):47-51.
 - 23-Junaid M, Siddique AN, Khan MT. Detection and prevalence of hepatitis B, C and HIV viral infections among hemophilia patients in Peshawar, Pakistan. JEZS. 2017;5(2):180-4.
 - 24-Ujjan ID, Memon RA, Butt AR, Sheikh IA, Khokhar GN, Yousfani GM, Farooq M. Seroprevalence of HBsAg and anti-HCV in healthy blood donors. Pak J Gastroenterol. 2006;20(1):75-77.
 - 25-Egah DZ, Mandong BM, Iya D, Gomwalk NE, Audu ES, Banwat EB, Onile BA. Hepatitis C virus antibodies among blood donors in Jos, Nigeria. 2004; 3(1):35-37.
 - 26-Isa AH, Hassan A, Mamman A, Bababdoko AA, Muktar HM, Ahmed AJ. Seroprevalence of hepatitis C virus antibodies amongst blood donors in Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH) Kaduna. African Journal of Clinical and Experimental Microbiology. 2010;11(2).
 - 27-Mumtaz S. Frequency of seropositive blood donors for hepatitis B, C and HIV viruses in railway hospital Rawalpindi. PJMR-Pakistan Journal of Medical Research. 2002;41(2):51-3.
 - 28-Chattoraj A, Behl R, Kataria VK. Infectious disease markers in blood donors. Medical Journal Armed Forces India. 2008 Jan 1;64(1):33-5.
 - 29-Kaur H, Dhanoa J, Pawar G. Hepatitis C infection amongst blood donors in Punjab-a six year study. Indian J Hematol Blood Transfus. 2001;19(2):21.
 - 30-Singh B, Verma M, Verma K. Markers for transfusion-associated hepatitis in north Indian blood donors: prevalence and trends. Japanese journal of infectious diseases. 2004 Apr 1;57(2):49-51.
 - 31-Arshad A, Borhany M, Anwar N, Naseer I, Ansari R, Boota S, Fatima N, Zaidi M, Shamsi T. Prevalence of transfusion transmissible infections in blood donors of Pakistan. BMC hematology. 2016 Dec;16(1):27-32.
 - 32-Khan A, Bukhari SS, Alvi MI, Qazi A. Seroprevalence of hepatitis B, hepatitis C and HIV in blood donors of Peshawar. Gomal Journal of Medical Sciences. 2010 Dec 31;9(1): 46-50.
 - 33-Murugan S, Devi PU, Selvi ST. Seroprevalence of HbsAg and Elevated Serum Alfafetoprotein among the Fishermen Community of Tuticorin, Tamil Nadu, South India. Journal Indian Academy of Clinical Medicine. 2010 Jul;11:180-3.
 - 34-Afolabi AY, Abraham A, Oladipo EK, Adefolarin AO, Fagbami AH. Transfusion transmissible viral infections among

potential Blood donors in Ibadan, Nigeria.
African Journal of Clinical and Experimental
Microbiology. 2013;14(2):84-7.